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Assessment and certification of health facility buildings: case study of the Basic Health Unit No. 5 of Riacho Fundo II, in Brasilia - Federal District

Rafael Santos Gonçalves de Assis MORAIS¹, Gerson Oliveira PENNA², Ana Luiza Alves de OLIVEIRA³,
João da Costa PANTOJA⁴

¹ Rehabilitation Laboratory of the Built Environment (LabRAC), University of Brasilia (UnB) and Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Fiocruz), Brasilia - DF, Brazil, rafaelsgam@gmail.com

² Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Fiocruz) and Medical School of University of Brasilia (UnB), Brasilia - DF, Brazil, gerson.penna@fiocruz.br

³ Rehabilitation Laboratory of the Built Environment (LabRAC), University of Brasilia (UnB), Brasilia - DF, Brazil, analuiza.aoliveira@gmail.com

⁴ Rehabilitation Laboratory of the Built Environment (LabRAC), University of Brasilia (UnB), Brasilia - DF, Brazil, joaocpantoja@gmail.com

Abstract: The quality of structural healthcare spaces is fundamental to ensuring well-being, safety and productivity, as well as promoting sustainable practices through rational cost management. This study analyses the quality and performance of the building housing Basic Health Unit No. 5 in Riacho Fundo II, Brasília - Federal District, applying a multi-parametric assessment and certification model. The study used an experimental design with *in loco* data collection, including visual and photographic inspections. Specific methodologies were applied to calculate depreciation, state of conservation, performance factor, cultural and heritage significance, degradation of the main and general elements and, finally, the quality and performance indicator. The unit scored poorly, with a quality and performance indicator of 54.45 per cent. The final certification indicated an overall classification in the D quality band, corresponding to a level of conservation that requires significant interventions for adequacy. The model applied identified deficiencies in conservation and functionality, suggesting the need for improvements to achieve adequate standards of performance and quality. The rating obtained reinforces the importance of preventive maintenance and rehabilitation policies to ensure the integrity and sustainability of healthcare spaces.

Keywords: Health Management; Health Facilities; Hospital Design and Construction; Public Health Surveillance; Sustainable Development.

1. Introduction

In Brazil, there are few research groups and institutions focussed on studies of the quality of the structural healthcare environment, and few devote time, intellectual and financial resources to the task, which is reflected in the small amount of theoretical output concerning the quality of healthcare buildings (MS, 2013). Thus, it is still common practice to restore a building only when it has reached critical levels of deterioration. According to Moreira (2011), the lack of a maintenance culture directly affects buildings, presenting itself as one of the challenges that refers not only to the technical and material dimensions, but also to the theoretical framework of conservation. Still according to the author, long-term preventive maintenance is currently one of the best strategies for conserving heritage assets, and the creation of inspection and periodic maintenance systems that can replace restoration work is recommended, as well as a management system aimed at conserving and sustaining real estate.

Maintenance, rehabilitation and improvement of built environments are ways of increasing performance and efficiency, and are advantageous compared to the construction of new spaces, due to both economic and financial aspects and environmental impact. Thus, these actions are advantageous not only from the point of view of sustainable - or ecologically responsible - development, but also because they have an economic and financial influence on the management of these buildings (Donegá, 2021).

Here, rehabilitation is understood as the set of operations aimed at conserving and restoring the significant parts - in historical, aesthetic and functional terms - of an architecture, including its general improvement, in order to enable it to meet updated performance levels and requirements. This concept can be applied both in the context of broad urban interventions and in interventions carried out on buildings. Upgrading, in turn, refers to rehabilitation aimed at achieving performance levels higher than the original design (LNEC, 2003, *apud* Paiva; Aguiar; Pinho, 2006).

Health facility buildings (EAS), like any other buildings, wear out over the course of their useful life, whether due to natural ageing and/or accidental external actions of human or natural origin. These changes compromise the performance of the functions for which they were designed and may even jeopardise the safety of occupants (Pantoja *et al.*, 2020).

Quality buildings and a functional environment are fundamental to guaranteeing the safety of users of the system and favouring comfort and welcome for users and professionals. In turn, welcoming as an attitude and practice in care and management actions in health units favours building a relationship of trust and commitment between users and the teams and services, contributing to promoting a culture of solidarity and legitimising the public health system. As a consequence, a quality healthcare space and an environment that favours comfort and welcome also bring the possibility of advances in the alliance between users, workers and healthcare managers in defence of the Unified Health System (SUS) as an essential public policy of and for the Brazilian population (MS, 2010).

EAS in Brazil are directly subject to the recommendations and guidelines of the Ministry of Health (MS) and, in addition, of regulatory bodies and inspectors, such as the National Health Surveillance Agency (*Anvisa*). With regard to the architectural planning of these buildings, the main consideration should be given to Collegiate Board Resolution 50 of 21 February 2002 (RDC 50) (*Anvisa*, 2002), which basically deals with the definition of the elements that make up healthcare equipment, their application and characteristics, as well as the requirements for operation.

This study helps managers make decisions about the importance and need to maintain healthcare spaces by providing regular and standardised data on the state of the structures, functionality and quality of the environments, making it possible to monitor the conditions of degradation and performance of these buildings, as yet another strategy for achieving the constitutional principles relating to the health of the population.

A multi-parametric model is proposed to qualify and quantify important variables in the study and assessment of the conservation and performance of healthcare facilities, which is then applied to the reference unit for the case study.

2. Method

This is an experimental study, followed by the proposal of a standardised assessment process using a multi-parametric model to qualify and quantify the state of conservation and performance of EAS and certification of buildings. The model was applied in a case study, providing data on the state of the structure, functionality and quality of the environments.

Data was collected during an on-site assessment of the reference unit, which resulted in documentary and photographic records that enabled the study to be finalised.

The assessment and certification process took place in ten stages, covering the aspects most pertinent to the study. The stages follow the logical sequence best suited to the type of assessment, systematising the various processes presented below.

2.1 Definition of assessment elements

Selected on the basis of RDC 50, they observe parameters that cover all the different types of EAS. According to the standard's classifications, fundamental elements have been selected for buildings to operate properly, ensuring a functional and safe environment, observing the following aspects: for appearance: assessment of the aesthetic conservation of environments; for functionality: flow analysis and spatial organisation; for safety: compliance with safety and accessibility standards; for environmental conditions for infection control: assessment of environmental requirements that minimise the risk of infections; for structural-functional organisation: structure and structural layout of internal elements; and for sizing and building installations: the suitability of dimensions and technical systems for the proper functioning of services.

2.2 Assessment of the state of conservation (C)

The units are classified according to the Heidecke criterion, with a Depreciation Coefficient (C) associated with the state of conservation. The criterion is a weighting that establishes that throughout the useful life of the building, the state of conservation defines how the damage will develop. Nine states of conservation are proposed (New = 0.000; Between new and regular = 0.003; Regular = 0.025; Between regular and simple repairs = 0.081; Simple repairs = 0.181; Between simple and major repairs = 0.332; Major repairs = 0.526; Between major and worthless repairs = 0.752; and Worthless = 1.000), determining the qualitative and quantitative correlation that aids visual inspection (Oliveira; Pantoja, 2021).

2.3 Building inspection using the GUT_C Method

Proposed by Oliveira and Pantoja (2021), the model stands out for its ease and rapid application for problem solving and risk management. Each of the elements in the matrix (Severity, Urgency and Tendency) has a specific function and is assessed for each attribute inspected, showing the impact and intensity that damage to the building can generate, the time needed to repair it and its potential for growth. The damage is then described qualitatively and scored according to the criteria for each element.

The values for Severity, Urgency and Tendency can correspond to five different grades, with weight and classification (None = 1; Low = 3; Medium = 6; High = 8; and Total = 10). The classification and scoring matrix presents specific criteria for assigning each of the grades (Oliveira; Pantoja, 2021). The final GUT_C value is calculated using equation (1):

$$GUT_C = \frac{(G + U + T) * (1 + C)}{60} \quad (1)$$

Where: G = weight adopted for severity; U = weight adopted for urgency; T = weight adopted for tendency; and C = Heidecke conservation status.

2.4 Assessment of cultural significance (I_{sc})

Cultural significance is assessed as proposed by Guimarães (2021). The variables analyse the values and their correlation in the historical context of the city, quantifying heritage values of use, economic attractiveness, history, art, culture, symbolism and antiquity.

For each of the values there are specific guidelines for inclusion or exclusion, indicating how the assessment should be carried out. In this context, "value" refers to the different qualities, characteristics, meanings, perceptions or associations attributed to the elements you wish to conserve, be they buildings, objects, sites or landscapes.

A score of 1 or 0 is given for each of the values. The attributes scored are added together to give the index on a scale ranging from 0 to 7. Subsequently, the average of the values for each attribute is calculated and a weight is applied to each one, taking into account the relevance of each attribute to the building.

The value found for I_{sc} defines the level of significance (Invasive = 0; No significance = 1; Some significance = 2 to 3; Considerable significance = 4 to 5; and Exceptional significance = 6 to 7).

2.5 Assessment of asset importance (I_p)

The weighted average of the I_{sc} multiplied by the weight of the evaluated attribute in relation to the highest possible value results in a value between 0 and 1 corresponding to the Heritage Importance, which indicates the importance according to the significance index. The I_p is parameterised, with 0 being the value corresponding to the building that has no heritage significance and 1 being the value corresponding to the building with the highest heritage representation for that social group.

The importance intervals according to I_p are: Unimportant = 0; Minor importance = $0.00 < I_{sc} \leq 0.25$; Medium importance = $0.25 < I_{sc} \leq 0.50$; High importance = $0.50 < I_{sc} \leq 0.75$; and Very high importance = $0.75 < I_{sc} \leq 1.00$ (Oliveira, 2023).

2.6 Degradation assessment (ID)

Degradation is assessed by finding defects during the building inspection, assessing the intensity, measuring the extent of the damage and assigning a description of the condition.

The parameters for classifying the importance of defects are Light, Serious or Critical. Intensity ranges from 1 to 3, being Low, Medium or High. Ranging from 1 to 5, corresponding to the following damage extent percentages: <2 per cent, 2–10 per cent, 10–30 per cent, 30–70 per cent, and ≥ 70 per cent. The parameterised condition is classified using a classification matrix that correlates the defect and its intensity to the extent of the damage, returning six possible classification ranges (0.17; 0.33; 0.50; 0.67; 0.83; and 1.00) with their respective descriptions: Bad; Severe; Poor; Fair; Good; and Excellent.

An assessment is made of the degradation of the main elements (DM), which is a measure of the level of intervention required on the elements, the value of which is the ratio between the average of the different element condition scores and the highest score for these conditions.

This is followed by the assessment of the degradation of the general elements (DG), which is the ratio between the sum of the degradation scores for each element and the sum of the maximum degradation scores.

The degradation indicator (ID) is then calculated, which allows the building to be placed between three reference intervals ($ID < 0.40$; $0.40 < ID < 0.55$; and $ID > 0.55$), corresponding to three levels of degradation: Non-existent or weak; Medium; and Very important. The ID is calculated according to equation (2):

$$ID = 1 - \sqrt{\left(\frac{(1 - DM)^2 + (1 - DG)^2}{2}\right)} \quad (2)$$

Where: DM = degradation of the main elements; DG = degradation of general elements.

In order to classify the condition and extent of degradation, the need for intervention and the extent of the problems observed are also assessed for each element. The score varies between 0 and 3 (Oliveira, 2023).

2.7 Determining the performance factor (D)

After calculating the degradation indicator (ID), Oliveira (2023) proposes four equations for calculating the performance factor (D), according to the characteristics of the buildings to be assessed and their purpose of use: Minimum (D_M), Intermediate (D_I), Superior (D_S) and Special (D_E).

Buildings with minimal performance are those that receive reduced investment in design quality, materials and construction. They are considered low durability buildings, intended for temporary occupation and subject to more intense maintenance cycles when compared to higher performance buildings. The same logic applies to intermediate and superior performance buildings, which require higher criteria and investment in the initial phase of their life cycle (Oliveira, 2023).

Special performance buildings, on the other hand, are those that propose studies of maintenance and conservation cycles, with the aim of maximising the quality of projects, materials, executive processes and preventive maintenance, while avoiding degradation mechanisms. This group includes cultural heritage sites, major bridges and viaducts, healthcare facilities, airport areas and other complex installations. In all these cases, the main characteristic is that their interruption would generate significant losses for the manager, whether private or public (Oliveira, 2023). The special performance curve is shown in equation (3):

$$D_E = -2.6868 * (ID)^3 + 4.3466 * (ID)^2 - 2.6683 * (ID) + 1.0000 \quad (3)$$

Where: ID = Degradation Indicator.

2.8 Estimated useful life of the building (ESL)

The reference useful life represents the expected useful life of the component or system, considering an ideal use and maintenance scenario. In other words, it is the estimated period that a component or system should last under ideal conditions of use and maintenance (ISO, 2008).

The value is estimated based on the Factor Method, presented by the ISO 15686-8:2008 standard, which evaluates components or systems under certain exposure conditions. It is expressed by a formula based on 7 variable factors that affect the reference useful life of the component analysed (Meira; Zanoni, 2020). The factors in ISO 15686-8:2008 are: Component quality level (Factor A), Design quality level (Factor B), Execution quality level (Factor C), Internal environment characteristics (Factor D), External environment characteristics (Factor E), Conditions of use (Factor F) and Maintenance level (Factor G) (ISO, 2008).

To quantify the factors, numerical values are assigned (0.6; 0.8; 1.0; 1.2) according to the criteria previously specified for evaluating each one during the assessment (Meira, 2019).

Factors A, B and C are related to the inherent characteristics of the construction elements. Factors D and E are related to indoor and outdoor environmental conditions, respectively. And factors F and G are related to operating/maintenance conditions. Once the seven factors have been assessed, the estimated useful life is the product of all of them.

2.9 Integrated Model for Quality and Performance Assessment (I_{QP})

By combining all the variables into a single indicator, buildings are assessed and certified with an emphasis on performance, while taking into account cultural, historical and longevity aspects, using the Quality and Performance Indicator (I_{QP}), shown in equation (4):

$$I_{QP} = 0.9 * D + 0.1 * \left(\frac{I_{sc}}{7} + I_p + \frac{ESL}{1.2^7} - GUT_c - ID \right) \quad (4)$$

Where: D = performance factor; I_{sc} = cultural significance; I_p = asset importance; ESL = estimated useful life; GUT_c = Assessment using the GUT_c methodology; ID = Degradation Indicator.

The formula prioritises the performance factor, with corrections based on cultural significance, heritage importance, estimated useful life, the urgency of the necessary interventions and the degradation indicator, arriving at a single indicator for certification.

2.10 Certification

In this study certification was carried out according to Oliveira's (2023) proposal, considering the causes and effects between degradation and performance, using the I_{QP} . The value of the I_{QP} , in percentage, classifies the building in one of the performance bands, from A to E.

Category A ($D_E > 95$ per cent) includes new or refurbished buildings in excellent condition with little visible damage. In category B (80 per cent $< D_E < 95$ per cent) semi-new buildings in good condition, with simple repairs that do not compromise their appearance or safety. In category C (60 per cent $< D_E < 80$ per cent) buildings that require specialised intervention due to visible faults in the systems. In category D (40 per cent $< D_E < 60$ per cent) buildings that require rigorous intervention, with noticeable damage that affects safety. In category E ($D_E < 40$ per cent) buildings that have significant damage, requiring in-depth analysis for possible renovation or reuse.

Table 1 details the classification bands for certification, which vary according to performance, measured in percentages.

Table 1 - Certification in PBE Edifica (2024) Seal performance bands and colors.

Certification	Performance	Examples
A	$D > 95\%$	New buildings or those that have undergone renovations covering all systems. The useful life of the project, in accordance with ABNT NBR 15575, is greater than 95 per cent of the normative reference parameters with records of the project and execution of the work. Little or no damage visible to the naked eye, even to sensitive systems such as paint or other finish coatings. The few repairs do not alter the original standard and do not affect the appearance, functionality or safety of the development.
B	$80\% < D < 95\%$	Semi-new buildings or buildings in an excellent state of repair. Little or no damage visible to the naked eye and the building systems and elements are in good appearance, functionality and safety. At most, simple repairs with an investment of no more than 2 per cent of the total value of the property on the ground, mostly in painting or cladding systems. Repairs alter the original standard, but maintain and do not affect the appearance, functionality or safety of the development.
C	$60\% < D < 80\%$	Buildings in need of intervention by companies specialising in finishing systems such as painting or coatings. Minor faults in the most used and functional systems, such as window frames, plumbing, rainwater, drainage and electrics. Damage visible to the naked eye, with reported faults in the aforementioned systems that can affect appearance, functionality and safety. The investment in renovations does not yet exceed 20 per cent of the total value of the property built on the site. Repairs must necessarily be carried out by specialised companies or professionals because they have to interfere with the original standard, altering the concepts of appearance, functionality and safety of the development.
D	$40\% < D < 60\%$	Buildings in need of rigorous intervention by specialised companies, especially in finishing systems such as painting and coatings. There are persistent faults in systems that are used more frequently and are more functional, such as window frames, plumbing, rainwater, drainage and electrics. Damage is recurrent and easily visible to the naked eye, isolating or impeding functionality and safety. Investment in renovations still does not exceed 50 per cent of the total value of the property built on the site. Repairs must necessarily be accompanied by specialised companies or professionals, including a possible analysis of reusing the building for another purpose.
E	$D < 40\%$	The building has significant damage and the investment in renovations exceeds 50 per cent of the total value of the property on the site. An in-depth analysis is required with the aim of restoring, rehabilitating, reusing or even recycling materials.

Source: Oliveira (2023), adapted by the author.

3. Analysing the case study

In the Federal District, in 2016, the National Public Tender for Architectural and Complementary Projects was held for Basic Health Unit No. 5 in Riacho Fundo II (UBS-5), in the Parque do Riacho Residential Centre. Promoted by the Federal District Housing Development Company (Codhab - DF), the competition saw Preliminary Study no. 270 win.

The winning project gave rise to UBS-5, inaugurated on 1 September 2021, which was soon recognised as the largest in Brazil (DF, 2021), gaining international repercussions for the modern and conceptual architectural standards that were used (Souza, 2024).

With a modernist architectural style, UBS-5 was built with reinforced concrete foundations and floor slabs. The pillars are made of metal, as is the roof support structure. The internal partitions are made of thermo-acoustic and waterproof compounds, covered with ceramic tiles when necessary, and the window frames are made of aluminium. It was designed and built on a single floor and organised into three modules made up of rectangular blocks with internal courtyards. **Figure 1** shows an aerial view of the unit, where you can see the three modules that make it up.

Figure 1 - Aerial view of UBS-5 from the left (north-east) elevation.

Source: Saboia+Ruiz Architects.

The facility's structural and functional programming is personalised and adapted to the specific needs of the locality. It has combined tasks and activities so that it is efficient and appropriate to the reality of the community.

Among the general duties and activities carried out at UBS-5 according to the RDC 50 classifications are: the provision of elective outpatient health promotion and care; health care including promotion, prevention, community health surveillance and outpatient care on a scheduled and ongoing basis; training and development of human resources and research; care related to health care and assistance in teaching and research functions; administrative functions and management support; and logistical support services.

4. Results

UBS-5 was classified as a regular building according to Heidecke's state of conservation. The classification is based on the building's deficiencies due to inadequate maintenance in the three years since its inauguration. Once the heritage values were analysed, the I_{sc} was 2, since only the use and artistic values were scored. The following weights were assigned: façades = 0.30; structural system = 0.35; architectural design = 0.20; and implementation = 0.15. Based on the average of the I_{sc} and the weight assigned to each system, the overall I_p of the building was 0.23, indicating that the building holds limited heritage significance, falling within the classification interval $0.00 < I_{sc} \leq 0.25$.

After assessing the criteria for evaluating factors A to G, the following values were assigned: Factor A = 1.0; Factor B = 1.2; Factor C = 1.0; Factor D = 1.0; Factor E = 1.0; Factor F = 1.2; and Factor G = 1.0. The product of the values gives $ESL = 1.44$.

The building inspection was carried out under the registration of the Technical Responsibility Term CRT/DF no. CFT2403672375, and the site visit took place on 16/07/2024. The final GUT_c value calculated for the building was 0.1887, corresponding to the arithmetic mean of the value of all the elements assessed.

The value found for the degradation of the main elements is 0.5555 and the value found for the degradation of the general elements is 0.0667. Using these values, the structure's degradation indicator is equal to 0.2690, or 26.90 per cent, classifying the structure's degradation as non-existent or weak. Thus, the value for the special performance factor is equal to 0.5445, or 54.45 per cent.

Using the values found for the performance factor, cultural significance, heritage importance, estimated useful life, GUT_c assessment and degradation indicator, it is possible to calculate a quality and performance indicator equal to 0.5360, or 53.60 per cent. UBS-5 is therefore certified in category D for quality and performance.

Table 2 shows the values for each of the parameters assessed, the value of the quality and performance indicator for each of the sets of elements and the respective certification range.

Table 2 - Results of the parameters assessed and certification bands for UBS-5.

Assessment/certification element	UBS-5	
Heidecke Conservation Status (C)	Regular (0.025)	
Building inspection using the GUT_c methodology (overall average)	0.1887	
Cultural Significance (I_{sc})	Some significance (2)	
Asset Importance (I_p)	Small (0.23)	
Degradation of the Main Elements (DM)	0.5555	
Degradation of General Elements (DG)	0.0667	
Degradation Indicator (DI)	0.2690 or 26.90%	
Performance Factor (D)	0.5445 or 54.45%	
Estimated useful life of the building (ESL)	1.44	
Quality and Performance Indicator (I_{qp})	Structural and functional organisation	49.83%
	Room sizing, quantification and building installations	48.83%
	Appearance	49.35%
	Functionality	49.07%
	Security	48.12%
	Environmental conditions for infection control	48.96%
General	53.60% D (40% < I_{qp} < 60%)	

Figure 2 shows the certification label for UBS-5 in category D for quality and performance, with an overall I_{qp} of 53.60 per cent.

Quality and Performance Health Facilities

Building: Riacho Fundo II Basic Health Unit No. 5 (UBS-5)

Type of unit: Health Centre/Basic Unit | CNES: 7526504

Address: QS 9, Complex 1, No. 1, Parque do Riacho - Riacho Fundo II

City and Federation Unit: Brasilia – Federal District

Evaluation date: 16/07/2024

New
 Regular
 Bottom
 Worthless

Higher quality and overall performance

Lower quality and overall performance

INFORMATION BY COMPONENT

Comments:

- The label is valid for 1 year.
- To check the full evaluation, follow the Qrcode opposite.

Figure 2 - UBS-5 certification label.

Source: Prepared by the author based on the model proposed by PBE Edifica (2024).

4. Discussion

UBS-5 showed a state of conservation with degradation in the main and general elements (ID of 26.90 per cent) and a medium performance factor (54.45 per cent), demonstrating the need for interventions indicating a low level of urgency, likely attributable to the absence of a preventive maintenance regime in the unit. The cultural significance and heritage importance are low (I_{sc} of 2 and I_p of 0.23), and the estimated useful life is good (1.44). As for certification, UBS-5 was classified in the D range for overall quality (I_{QD} of 53.60 per cent), indicating that the unit requires improvement to reach the appropriate level of quality and performance.

The weaknesses in the process of conserving this space present a challenge for the state's commitment to valorising heritage as collective assets of the population, as well as guaranteeing access to quality health services.

5. Conclusions

By maintaining and enhancing healthcare buildings, the public sector upholds both its duty to cultural preservation and its role in delivering inclusive, high-performing services that reflect the values of public health. This integrated approach contributes to a resilient healthcare infrastructure, strengthens the identity of the community, and promotes sustainable urban development.

As well as adding value to assets, a safe, high-quality structural environment has a positive impact on patient adherence to health services, contributing to regular access to preventive care. This quality not only improves the user experience, but reinforces the population's commitment to health, promoting prevention and continuity of care.

The impact of this care translates into a more efficient service, reinforcing the system's ability to respond to users' needs. In this way, the SUS benefits from a more resilient infrastructure and planning that supports the population in a comprehensive and continuous way, aligned with the principles of universality and equity that underpin Brazil's Unified Health System.

In the context of the Federal District, where architecture is an inseparable part of the landscape and the urban imagination, preservation initiatives combined with the functionality of healthcare spaces are fundamental for urban development and social well-being. It also reinforces the population's identity and sense of belonging.

Thus, maintaining UBS-5 at excellent levels of quality and performance adds value to public health in the Federal District and highlights the importance of preserving built heritage.

References

- ANVISA - National Health Surveillance Agency (BR) / Collegiate Board. Resolution-RDC no. 50, of 21 February 2002. Brasília - DF, 2002. https://bvsms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/anvisa/2002/res0050_21_02_2002.html
- DF - Federal District (BR). International website highlights UBS-5 in Riacho Fundo II. Brasília - DF: Agência Brasília, 2021. Available at: <https://www.agenciabrasilia.df.gov.br/2021/09/15/site-internacional-destaca-ubs-5-do-riacho-fundo-ii/>. Accessed on: 14 Nov. 2024.
- DONEGÁ A. A. Morphological performance of healthcare facilities via building inspection [dissertation]. University of Brasília, Brasília - DF, 2021. <https://repositorio.unb.br/handle/10482/42963>
- GOMIDE T. L. F.; NETO J. C. P. F.; GULLO M. A. Total Building Inspection: guidelines and reports in the approach of total quality and diagnostic engineering. São Paulo: Pini, 3rd ed., 2020. https://www.ofitexto.com.br/inspecao_predial_total_3ed/p
- GUIMARÃES L. R. N. Evaluation of heritage assets via coupled models of depreciation and cultural significance: The case of CEF-Metropolitan, Núcleo Bandeirante - DF [dissertation]. University of Brasília. Brasília - DF. 2021. <https://repositorio.unb.br/handle/10482/43093>

- ISO - International Organisation for Standardization. ISO 15686-8:2008 Buildings and constructed assets - Service-life planning - Part 8: Reference service life and service-life estimation. Geneva. 2008. <https://www.iso.org/standard/39070.html>
- MEIRA I. O. Vulnerability indicator for conservation management of buildings of cultural value: a study applied to modernist museums [dissertation]. University of Brasília. Brasília - DF. 2019. <http://repositorio2.unb.br/jspui/handle/10482/47458>
- MEIRA I. O.; ZANONI V. A. G. Vulnerability Indicator for Conservation Management of Buildings of Cultural Value. Paranoá, 13(26), 157-174. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.18830/issn.1679-0944.n26.2020.11>
- MH - Ministry of Health (BR). Acolhimento nas práticas de produção de saúde. 2nd ed. Brasília - DF: Editora do Ministério da Saúde, 2010. https://bvsmis.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/acolhimento_praticas_producao_saude.pdf
- MH - Ministry of Health (BR). Architectural Programming of Functional Health Units. SOMASUS - Sistema de Apoio à Elaboração de Projetos de Investimentos em Saúde. (Architectural Programming of Functional Health Units, v. 3) Brasília - DF: Ministry of Health, 2013. https://bvsmis.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/soma_sus_sistema_apoio_elaboracao_vol3.pdf
- MOREIRA F. D. The challenges posed by the conservation of modern architecture. Revista CPC, (11), 152-187, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.11606/issn.1980-4466.v0i11p152-187>
- OLIVEIRA I. P. Criteria for certification and evaluation of buildings: an integrated approach to degradation and performance [thesis]. University of Brasília, Brasília - DF. 2023. <http://repositorio.unb.br/handle/10482/49407>
- OLIVEIRA I. P.; PANTOJA J. C. Proposal to analyse the Historical Heritage of the Cláudio Santoro National Theatre - Brasília. ReBEFA, [S.l.], v. 6, n. 2, jul. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.15170490>
- PAIVA J. V.; AGUIAR J.; PINHO A. Guia técnico de reabilitação habitacional. 1st ed. Lisbon: LNEC, 2006, 2 vol, 467 p. <http://id.bnportugal.gov.pt/bib/bibnacional/1690301>
- PANTOJA JC, MOURA SPN, VARUM H, CAIED S. The Influence of Weighting in the Evaluation of the Degree of Criticality in Multi-Floor Buildings via Building Inspection. Paranoá, [S. l.], n. 26, p. 126-139, 2020. <https://periodicos.unb.br/index.php/paranoa/article/view/30460>
- BRAZILIAN BUILDING ETIQUETAGING PROGRAMME (PBE Edifica). About PBE Edifica. Available at: <https://www.pbeedifica.com.br/sobre>. Accessed on: 16 Apr. 2025.
- SILVA D. S. T. Management and conservation of Brasília's heritage: A comparative study between Brazilian and international inspection methodologies [dissertation]. University of Brasília, Brasília - DF. 2022. <http://repositorio2.unb.br/jspui/handle/10482/45025>
- SOUZA E. 1st place in the competition for the Basic Health Unit in Parque do Riacho - Codhab-DF. Brazil: ArchDaily Brazil, 2017. Available at: <https://www.archdaily.com.br/br/874775/1o-lugar-no-concurso-para-a-unidade-basica-de-saude-em-parque-do-riacho-codhab-df>. Accessed on: 14 Nov. 2024.